

Time-varying compartmental models with neural networks for pandemic infection forecasting

Marianna Karapitta, Andreas Kasis, Charithea Stylianides, Kleantlis Malialis, Panayiotis Kolios

Abstract—The emergence and spread of deadly pandemics has repeatedly occurred throughout history, causing widespread infections and life loss. Forecasting the progression of pandemics is crucial for decision-makers to achieve its mitigation. This predictive task constitutes a challenge due to the non-stationary nature of pandemics, and changes in adopted policies and social reactions to them. Motivated by this, we present a hybrid pandemic infection forecasting methodology that integrates compartmental modelling and machine learning approaches. In particular, we develop a compartmental model that includes time-varying infection rates, which are the key parameters that determine a pandemic’s evolution. To identify the time-dependent infection rates, we establish a hybrid methodology that combines the developed compartmental model and tools from optimization and neural networks. Specifically, the proposed methodology estimates the infection rates by fitting the model to the available data, regarding the COVID-19 pandemic in Cyprus, and then predicting their future values through either a) extrapolation, or b) using neural networks. The developed approach exhibits strong accuracy in predicting infections seven days in advance, achieving low average percentage errors both using the extrapolation (9.90%) and neural network (5.04%) approaches.

Index Terms—epidemiology, forecasting, infections, compartmental models, machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Motivation: Over the years, numerous pandemics have caused a significant burden on global economies and public health. An early pandemic with devastating effects was due to Cholera. The first of seven cholera pandemics emerged in India (1817) and was caused by the ingestion of food or water contaminated with the bacterium *Vibrio cholerae* [1]. Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (2003) is believed to have possibly originated from bats and spread to humans in China and was disseminated through respiratory droplets [2]. Quarantine efforts proved effective in controlling the virus, and since then the disease has not reappeared.

In December 2019, a “pneumonia of unknown etiology” was reported in Wuhan, China [3]. It was soon identified as

The authors are with the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus, 2103 Nicosia, Cyprus (e-mails: mariannakarapitta@gmail.com; kasis.andreas@ucy.ac.cy; charitheastylianides@gmail.com; malialis.kleantlis@ucy.ac.cy; kolios.panayiotis@ucy.ac.cy).

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the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, now known as COVID-19. The fast transmission of the virus prompted the World Health Organization to declare it a pandemic. Governments globally implemented various intervention measures to curtail the spread of the disease, resulting in significant disruptions to economies and societies [4]. Studies have examined trade-offs between pandemic effects and the economic impact of interventions, proposing strategies [5].

Modelling and forecasting the disease’s spread is key for the assessment of its transmissibility, and the design of suitable intervention measures [6]. Predicting the growth of infections may inform governments and healthcare professionals about an upcoming wave, and enable appropriate intervention strategies. Thus, accurately predicting infections is critical for effectively managing a pandemic.

Related work: Compartmental models have proved to be valuable instruments in describing infectious disease epidemics and facilitating the characterization of their asymptotic behaviour and dependence on model parameters [7]. Various approaches to model and predict the progression of the COVID-19 outbreak rely on these models. A classic example of a compartmental model is the Susceptible (S), Infected (I), Recovered (R) model [8], where the variation of each compartment with time is described by a set of equations with suitable parameters describing the rates of transition among states. More complicated models involve additional compartments and parameters.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, certain parameters in compartmental models play a crucial role in determining its progression. Given the continuous evolution of dominant variants and the impact of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, precise modeling of pandemic behavior is essential. Studies have therefore explored compartmental models with time-varying parameters to assess influencing factors such as vaccine availability, government measures, environmental conditions, and virus’ features changes. For instance studies [9, 10] employ these models to capture the COVID-19 dynamics in Italy and forecast its spread in the United States, respectively.

Efforts for precise modelling of the COVID-19 pandemic behaviour, considering possible influencing factors on its evolution, have used Machine Learning approaches [11, 12]. These factors and the non-stationary behaviour of the SARS-CoV-2 virus motivated the use of incremental learning approaches, which delivered improved predictions enabling the

necessary flexibility to achieve optimized solutions [13, 14]. There exist studies that are solely incremental learning-based [15, 16], and studies using hybrid methodologies combining incremental learning of neural networks to identify parameters involved in compartmental models [17, 18]. A gap in the literature is to examine the predictive abilities of learning-based approaches on compartmental models with time-varying parameters. Such approach has the potential to harness the advantages of both types of approaches, enabling enhanced modelling flexibility through time-varying compartmental models and strong predictive accuracy through the use of machine learning.

Contribution: This paper develops and studies a time-varying compartmental model designed to describe the evolution of a pandemic. The model incorporates time-dependent infection rates, which constitute the key parameters that determine the evolution of the pandemic. The time-varying rates are identified by a hybrid approach that combines the proposed compartmental model with machine learning approaches. In particular, our study utilizes the available data to estimate the time-varying parameters of the model. Subsequently, predictions of their future values are obtained through either a) extrapolation, or b) the employment of neural networks. The neural networks are trained by incremental learning, allowing the continual adaptation of the time-varying rates to the non-stationary characteristics of the pandemic. The produced infection rates are then utilized through the proposed compartmental model to enable predictions of the infected population. The developed approach demonstrates high predictive accuracy for future infections seven days in advance, with low average percentage errors observed through both extrapolation (9.90%) and neural network (5.04%) approaches.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- (i) We propose a compartmental model that involves time-dependent infection rates, which are the parameters with the largest impact on the pandemic progression.
- (ii) We establish a hybrid approach, that combines the proposed time-varying compartmental model with machine learning, for predicting future infections. The developed methodology achieves significantly low average percentage errors in predicting future infections seven days in advance, both through extrapolation (9.90%) and neural network (5.04%) approaches.

Paper structure: Section II describes the proposed model and the developed methodologies used to identify the time-varying infection rates and to predict the infected population. Then, Section III presents the results associated with the identification of the rates and the predictive accuracy, in terms of future infections, of the proposed methodology. Section IV presents the conclusions of this paper. It should be noted that additional explanations on this work's methodology have been omitted due to space constraints, and are available in [19], which is an extended version of this work.

II. METHODS

This section outlines the methodologies developed in this study. Firstly, Section II-A introduces the designed compartmental model, along with its time-varying parameters to be identified. Subsequently, Section II-B explains the model-based procedure utilized for estimating the optimized time-dependent parameters, followed by Section II-C that describes the learning-based approach for predicting the parameters' future values, based on the previously identified model-based results. Finally, Section II-D provides the method followed for predicting the infected population and the evaluation methodology of the model's predictive accuracy.

A. The SIDAREVH compartmental model

The SIDAREVH compartmental model is a deterministic model developed to characterize the progression of pandemics. The model was named SIDAREVH, after its compartments, into which it partitions the investigated population. The proposed compartments are: susceptible (S), unvaccinated infected detected (I), vaccinated infected detected (D), unvaccinated hospitalized (A), recovered (R), extinct (E), vaccinated susceptible (V), and vaccinated hospitalized (H). These compartments were selected to include all our available data regarding the COVID-19 pandemic in Cyprus. A schematic representation of the SIDAREVH model is shown in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. The SIDAREVH compartmental model.

The dynamics of the SIDAREVH model are given by (1). The $s, i, d, \alpha, r, e, v, h \in [0, 1]$ are the states of the system, describing the population percentage of susceptible, unvaccinated infected, vaccinated infected, unvaccinated hospitalized, recovered, extinct, vaccinated susceptible, and vaccinated hospitalized, respectively.

$$\dot{s} = -\beta_{uu}is - \beta_{vu}ds - \zeta s, \quad (1a)$$

$$\dot{i} = \beta_{uu}is + \beta_{vu}ds - \xi_i i - \gamma_i i, \quad (1b)$$

$$\dot{d} = \beta_{vv}iv + \beta_{uv}dv - \xi_d d - \gamma_d d \quad (1c)$$

$$\dot{\alpha} = \xi_i i - \gamma_a \alpha - \mu_a \alpha, \quad (1d)$$

$$\dot{r} = \gamma_i i + \gamma_d d + \gamma_a \alpha + \gamma_h h, \quad (1e)$$

$$\dot{e} = \mu_\alpha \alpha + \mu_h h, \quad (1f)$$

$$\dot{v} = \zeta s - \beta_{vv} i v - \beta_{uv} d v, \quad (1g)$$

$$\dot{h} = \xi_d d - \gamma_h h - \mu_h h. \quad (1h)$$

The SIDAREVH model includes a large number of parameters that describe the transition rates between its compartments. Table I provides a brief description of each rate. We assume that all parameter values are known and constant, except the four infection rates β_{uu} , β_{vu} , β_{vv} , and β_{uv} . These are the key parameters that govern the pandemic dynamics since they determine the effect of the included bilinear terms in (1), and hence have the largest impact on the progression of the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, these parameters are assumed to be time-varying due to the effect of influencing factors on them, such as government intervention measures [20], environmental temperature and humidity [21, 22], and changing dominant variants [23]. The constant parameters involved in the SIDAREVH model have a smaller impact on the pandemic infections, they were obtained from existing literature studies and are substantiated in [19].

TABLE I
DESCRIPTION OF SIDAREVH MODEL'S PARAMETERS.

Symbol	Description
ζ	Rate of vaccination of susceptible individuals
β_{uu}	Unvaccinated to unvaccinated infection rate
β_{vu}	Vaccinated to unvaccinated infection rate
β_{vv}	Vaccinated to vaccinated infection rate
β_{uv}	Unvaccinated to vaccinated infection rate
γ_i	Recovery rate for unvaccinated infected
γ_d	Recovery rate for vaccinated infected
γ_α	Recovery rate for unvaccinated hospitalized
γ_h	Recovery rate for vaccinated hospitalized
ξ_i	Hospitalization rate for unvaccinated infected
ξ_d	Hospitalization rate for vaccinated infected
μ_α	Unvaccinated hospitalized to decrease rate
μ_h	Vaccinated hospitalized to decrease rate

The SIDAREVH model is based on the following assumptions, that constitute theoretical requirements for compartmental models:

- (i) The considered population is constant and isolated.
- (iii) Infected individuals become first hospitalized before they decrease.
- (iv) Vaccinations are performed on susceptible individuals.
- (v) Recovered and vaccinated individuals cannot be susceptible again.

B. Model-based infection rates estimation

This section describes the methodology employed for the estimation of the time-varying infection rates β_{uu} , β_{vu} , β_{vv} , β_{uv} included in the proposed SIDAREVH model. These four parameters are associated with the bilinear terms within the dynamics of (1), and constitute the parameters with the largest impact on the evolution of the infected cases in the pandemic. They are considered to vary over time since are affected by various factors, such as government policies, and environmental and virus characteristics. Estimates of the infection

rates were produced by fitting the SIDAREVH model to the observed data. The procedure is made through seven- and fourteen-day sliding windows, which moved by one day per increment.

To estimate the parameter values, we aim to minimize the optimization cost function:

$$C_j(n, i, d, \hat{i}_j, \hat{d}_j) = \sum_{t=j+1}^{j+n} [(i(t) - \hat{i}_j(t))^2 + (d(t) - \hat{d}_j(t))^2], \quad (2)$$

where C_j describes the deviations at day j , between the infected cases of data ($i(t)$ are the unvaccinated infected and $d(t)$ are the vaccinated infected) and predictions ($\hat{i}_j(t)$ are the estimated unvaccinated infected and $\hat{d}_j(t)$ vaccinated infected population using the knowledge available at time j), for a time window of size $n \in \{7, 14\}$.

The procedure to estimate the time-varying infection rates is as follows. Firstly, a referenced trial parameters set is created, by the initialization of the four infection rates, and an initial cost is determined. Subsequently, each of the four rates is increased and decreased by a constant percentage defining a new trial parameters set and a new cost is calculated for each modified rate. Then, the minimum cost within the current trial parameters set is identified and compared to the minimum cost from the preceding iteration. If the minimum cost resulted in a decreased cost compared to the previous iteration, the considered modified infection rate is kept and used for the subsequent iterations, creating a new set of trial parameters. This iterative process is applied for all the sliding windows of the examined period until the set of parameters that minimizes the cost of each window is found. Finally, four sets of optimal infection rates, denoted by $\vec{\beta}_{uu}$, $\vec{\beta}_{vu}$, $\vec{\beta}_{vv}$, and $\vec{\beta}_{uv}$, are obtained, containing the parameters' time-dependent values that best describe each considered n -day window.

C. Learning-based infection rates prediction

This section presents the methodology employed for the prediction of the future values of the four infection rates β_{uu} , β_{vu} , β_{vv} , β_{uv} associated with the SIDAREVH model. The values of the parameters were predicted a week ahead using a neural network for each parameter.

Data preprocessing. The infection rates, as generated by the method explained in Section II-B, are normalized in the range $[0, 1]$ by dividing them with the largest value of the time series. Outliers (typically, very small values, e.g., less than 0.1) have been removed through visual inspection of data plots. Linear interpolation is used to fill in missing values due to outlier removal.

We consider the set $\mathcal{B} = \{\vec{\beta}_{uu}, \vec{\beta}_{vu}, \vec{\beta}_{vv}, \vec{\beta}_{uv}\}$, of the four infection rates sets, after the preprocessing procedure. Without any loss of generality, let $\vec{\beta} \in \mathcal{B}$ be any of the aforementioned infection rate sets. Each $\vec{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^T$, $T \in [1, \infty)$ constitutes a univariate time series, defined as $\vec{\beta} = \{\beta^j\}_{j=1}^T$, where j is the current day, and β^j is the infection rate at day j .

Role of the window size W . To address the temporal correlations encountered in the time-series data, we

use a sliding or “lookback” window, such that, $\hat{\beta}^j = \{\beta^j, \beta^{j-1}, \dots, \beta^{j-W+1}\} \in \mathbb{R}^W$ where $W \in \mathbb{N}$ is the window size. We assessed our proposed method using two lookback window sizes $W \in \{7, 14\}$.

Learning models. We also consider a set of four regression models as $\mathcal{F} = \{f_{uu}, f_{vu}, f_{vv}, f_{uv}\}$, each corresponding to a time series $\vec{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ used for forecasting. Each model (one for each rate) is a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) model, which is a standard feed-forward fully connected neural network. All hyper-parameter values of the MLPs are reported in [19].

At each day $j \geq W + n - 1$ (where $n = T - W - D + 1$ is the total number of predictions made), the aim is to forecast the corresponding infection rate D days later, (we predict each rate $\hat{\beta}^{j+D}$ a week ahead, i.e., $D = 6$), by using $\hat{\beta}^j$. Without any loss of generality, let $f_\theta \in \mathbb{F}$ be a regression model (e.g., a neural network) parameterised by θ , defined as $f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^W \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, such that, $\hat{\beta}^{j+D} = f_\theta(\hat{\beta}^j)$. At any day $j \geq W + D$, the loss function used between a prediction $\hat{\beta}^j = f_\theta(\hat{\beta}^{j-D})$ and ground truth β^j is the Mean Squared Error (MSE) defined as $L^j = (\hat{\beta}^j - \beta^j)^2$.

The model gradually adapts without complete re-training using incremental learning, that is, $f_\theta^j = f_\theta^{j-1}.train(\hat{\beta}^{j-D}, \beta^j)$. It is continually updated using the online Stochastic Gradient Descent approach (or any Gradient Descent-based algorithm) where each model parameter $\theta_i \in \theta$ is updated according to the formula $\theta_i^j \leftarrow \theta_i^{j-1} - \alpha \frac{\partial L^j}{\partial \theta_i}$, where $\frac{\partial L^j}{\partial \theta_i}$ is the partial derivative with respect to θ_i , θ_i^j denotes the update in the j th iteration of θ_i , and α is the learning rate.

Evaluation methodology. All experiments are evaluated according to the widely used regression forecast metric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), as defined in (3). Furthermore, all experiments are run over ten repetitions.

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=W+D}^T \frac{|\beta^t - \hat{\beta}^t|}{|\beta^t|} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

D. Infected population prediction and evaluation

The methodology presented in this section is employed to forecast the targeted infected population. The SIDAREVH model’s parameterization enabled the forecasting procedure of both vaccinated and unvaccinated infected individuals. Predictions are made by extrapolating the infection rates identified firstly in Section II-B through the model’s fitting to the data, and by using the infection rates determined in Section II-C through neural networks. The predictions were developed in sliding windows of size $n \in \{7, 14\}$, using the information from the corresponding previous windows of the same size, all moving by one day per increment. The SIDAREVH model’s predictive accuracy is validated by the commonly employed metric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), defined as:

$$MAPE_j(n, i, d, \hat{i}_j, \hat{d}_j) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=j+1}^{j+n} \left| \frac{\hat{i}_j(t) + \hat{d}_j(t)}{i(t) + d(t)} - 1 \right| \times 100\%, \quad (4)$$

where $MAPE_j$ describes the average percentage error on day j , between the observed infected individuals from data ($i(t)$ are the unvaccinated and $d(t)$ are the vaccinated infected) and the predicted infected individuals ($\hat{i}_j(t)$, $\hat{d}_j(t)$) at time t , based on the information available up to time j . The values of \hat{i} and \hat{d} are presumed non-negative at all times. MAPEs were computed for all the sliding windows of the investigated timeframe yielding a set of MAPEs for all the windows of prediction. The mean and the associated standard deviation (S.D.) of the aforementioned set of MAPEs were calculated and presented in the next section.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides the main results concerning the accuracy of our methodologies, for the identification of the time-varying infection rates, associated with the developed SIDAREVH model, in predicting future infections.

A. Model-based and learning-based prediction of infected population

The forecasting error results demonstrated below are generated following the methodology explained in Section II-D, using the data of the preceding window of seven days, to the next window of seven days. The corresponding results of fourteen-day windows of predictions and the identified infection rates through the two approaches, are presented in [19].

Firstly, the SIDAREVH model’s predictive accuracy is presented in Table II. The presented values are calculated using the four optimized model-based infection rates, extrapolated at each day, in windows of seven days, filtered from outliers, as explained by the methodology described in Section II-B. The results show a MAPE (S.D.) of 9.90% (8.05%), which decreases to 8.70% (6.22%) when the highest 5% of errors are excluded.

TABLE II
SIDAREVH MODEL’S ACCURACY IN DESCRIBING THE INFECTED POPULATION DATA USING MODEL-BASED OPTIMIZED FILTERED TIME-VARYING INFECTION RATES WITH SEVEN-DAY WINDOWS.

	MAPE	S.D.
All data	9.90%	8.05%
Lowest 95% of errors	8.70%	6.22%

The forecasting error results of Table III are created utilising the learning-based infection rates predicted using lookback windows of fourteen days, as described in the methodology outlined in Section II-C. It is important to clarify that the window for the infection rates model-based estimation, which was selected to be seven days, is different than the fourteen-day lookback window of the learning-based prediction which determines how many past values of infection rate estimates are considered for prediction. This learning-based approach enables a MAPE (S.D.) of 5.04% (7.03%), which drops to 3.74% (4.27%) when the highest 5% error values are excluded. These results illustrate a significant improvement in terms of forecasting accuracy, compared to the results presented in Table II.

TABLE III
SIDAREVH MODEL'S ACCURACY IN DESCRIBING THE INFECTED
POPULATION DATA USING LEARNING-BASED PREDICTED TIME-VARYING
INFECTION RATES WITH SEVEN-DAY WINDOWS.

	MAPE	S.D.
All data	5.04%	7.03%
Lowest 95% of errors	3.74%	4.27%

IV. CONCLUSION

This study developed a compartmental model, suitable for characterizing the progression of pandemics, that includes time-varying infection rates, which are the key parameters with the largest impact on a pandemic's evolution. In addition, it presented a methodology to enable accurate predictions of future infections. In particular, the model's time-varying parameters were identified by a hybrid method that integrates compartmental mathematical modelling and machine learning. First, we estimated the infection rate values by fitting the available data, regarding the COVID-19 pandemic in Cyprus, to the proposed model and by extrapolating them, we forecast the infected population seven days ahead with a mean absolute percentage error of 9.90%. Then, we used neural regression models trained by incremental learning, to predict the infection rates as they were generated by the model-based estimations, and we observed an improvement in the predictive accuracy of our model, with a mean absolute percentage error of 5.04%. The proposed hybrid approach consists a reliable forecasting method for the progression of the infected cases, and can timely notify governments and healthcare professionals for a forthcoming crisis, and aid in the protection of the public community. In future work, we aim to conduct a comparative analysis between the developed approach and existing methodologies documented in the literature.

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